

End-to-End Digital Timber Tracking from Forest to Sawmill: Data Traceability Platform System (DTPS)

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable management of Mediterranean forest resources requires robust traceability and regulatory compliance across the entire timber supply chain, a challenge amplified by dual economic and environmental pressures and by the stringent requirements of new legislation like the EUDR. The Data Traceability Platform System (DTPS) directly addresses this need by enabling verifiable, end-to-end tracking of wood products, from standing trees to sawn timber, through a fully integrated digital solution designed to create an unimpeachable ‘digital passport’ for every asset.

This paper presents the initial implementation of the DTPS, analyzed through a qualitative case study framework to evaluate its architecture, data workflows, and operational processes. Developed within the Horizon Project *DigiMedFor*, the system integrates three core components: a central web-based Gateway that serves as the primary interface for data management and blockchain synchronization; an Android mobile application for in-field data capture, including RFID tagging and wood log measurements; and an innovative, drone-mounted Traceability Box.

The methods for data collection are founded on a hybrid technological approach, utilizing UHF RFID for unique wood identification, a private blockchain for creating secure and immutable transactional records, and, critically, authenticated drone surveys via a Galileo OSNMA-enabled receiver to certify no-deforestation practices with tamper-proof geospatial evidence.

The results of the implementation confirm a highly functional platform capable of serving a wide range of users, such as forest managers, logging companies, sawmills, and auditors, and of managing both single-operator and complex multi-actor supply chains. The system’s collection of highly descriptive data, such as time stamps, geolocation, and qualitative and quantitative information, forms a comprehensive digital thread between the forest and the wooden product.

The platform's capability to provide detailed traceability reports is one of its main outcomes. These reports provide auditable, verifiable evidence of legal origin and sustainable harvesting procedures, directly meeting the EUDR's due diligence criteria. They integrate all gathered data, including the certified drone positions, and provide access to blockchain record via unique QR codes.

In conclusion, the DTTPS is capable of accurately showing that a hybrid-technology, integrated system can transform the field of forestry into a digitalized environment. The combination of RFID authenticated GNSS and blockchain into one solution enables the platform to address the gaps between the complex requirements at the high level and the operational environment of the timber industry. The framework strengthens transparency and legal and provable sustainability, thus making it less risky for operators and more accessible to the market for compliant products. The model is not just a method of regulatory compliance, but it also puts in place a scalable and robust framework for the timber value chain.

KEYWORDS: Timber Traceability, RFID, Blockchain, Sustainable Forest Management, Supply Chain Management, No-deforestation, Galileo OSNMA, Data Integrity.

Abbreviations:

DTTPS: Data Traceability Platform System

EUDR: European Union Deforestation-Free Regulation

GNSS: Global Navigation Satellite System

OSNMA: Open Service Navigation Message Authentication

RFID: Radio Frequency Identification

UHF: Ultra High Frequency